

Supplementary Material 3. List of excluded or doubtful taxa.

Phylum	Reference
Ascomycota	
<i>Botryconis ocoteae</i>	Gómez and Kisimova-Horovitz 1997
<i>Cilicipodium costaricensis</i>	Spegazzini 1918, Covington 1980
<i>Cilicipodium sanguineum</i>	Bommer and Rousseau 1896, Covington 1980
<i>Colletotrichum cesatii</i>	Sydow 1926, Covington 1980
<i>Coniothyrium repens</i>	Goos 1960, Granados-Montero et al. 2018
<i>Cordyceps cassiicola</i>	Blanco 2022
<i>Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti</i>	Blanco 2022
<i>Gibberella intermedia</i>	Blanco 2022
<i>Helvella didicusana</i>	Gómez 1974, Calonge et al. 2006
<i>Hypocrella tompsonii</i>	Liu et al. 2005
<i>Neopestalotiopsis paeoniicola</i>	Blanco 2022
<i>Phaeodimeriella stevensii</i>	Sydow 1926, Covington 1980
<i>Phaeosphaeria guarantica</i>	Arguedas 2008
<i>Phyllachora stahlii</i>	Sáenz and Lizano 1981
<i>Stilbella flavida</i>	Hennings 1902, Covington 1980
<i>Sucinaria thomasianae</i>	Sydow 1925, Covington 1980
<i>Talaromyces diversum</i>	Blanco 2022
<i>Virgatospora swetasakha</i>	Morris 1972, Covington 1980
<i>Xylaria poculiformis</i>	Rowlee 1924, Covington 1980
Basidiomycota	
<i>Aecidium tobulosum</i>	Arthur 1918, Covington 1980, Berndt 2004
<i>Calocera flammea</i>	Fries 1851
<i>Eriosporangium exornatum</i>	Sydow 1925, Covington 1980, Berndt 2004
<i>Eriosporangium fidelis</i>	Sydow 1926, Covington 1980, Berndt 2004
<i>Junghuhnia straminea</i>	Carranza and Ruiz-Boyer 2005
<i>Polyporus peltatus</i>	Fries 1851
<i>Puccinia eytrariae</i>	Arthur 1918, Covington 1980
<i>Saccablastia avispara</i>	Kisimova-Horovitz et al. 2000a
<i>Saccablastia sphaerospara</i>	Kisimova-Horovitz et al. 2000a
<i>Tilletia oplismeni</i>	Piepenbring 1996